

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And well-Being In small and medium size ciTies

D5.1 Toolkit for Stakeholders' Engagement with a Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion perspective

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on the engagement of vulnerable groups and section 7.3 on measuring engagement.

- Increased bibliography to include references on the inclusion of vulnerable groups
- Inclusion of figures 8 and 23, and tables 6 and 7 for clarity

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The IN-HABIT Toolkit aims to provide a set of guidelines, methods and tools for the wider engagement of stakeholders in the People-public-private partnerships (PPPPs). It includes instructions for stakeholders mapping and local needs assessment, selection criteria, structure, working rules and diversity management procedures, co-design methodology, and the necessary guidelines and templates for the creation and management of the four local IN-HUBs. The Toolkit is the basis for the training process of the Local Community Activators and provides the reference set for the management of the four local IN-HUBS established in the cities of Córdoba, Lucca, Nitra, and Riga. It supports the accomplishment of a fully inclusive process of co-creation, co-design, co-management, and co-monitoring of the innovative solutions envisioned by the four local PPPPs, with specific attention at the engagement of less represented and more at risk of exclusion stakeholders.

The toolkit includes the Glossary, providing definitions of the main terms adopted by the project as agreed among the partners, the Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GDEI) guidelines, aimed at supporting the wider, just and equal participation of all social groups to the process, and the IN-HUBs Management guidelines, which provide tools and templates for setting the local PPPPs coordination structure, co-monitoring procedures, and to support the co-creation of innovative solutions with citizens and stakeholders.

This Toolkit is a living set of guidelines, methods and tools, and it will be adapted throughout the entire process based on the needs coming from the contextual application to the issues of the territories and the feedback of the local communities using it. Its purpose is to provide a set of flexible instruments to support the development of solutions tailored to the peculiarities of the local communities and to support their transferability to other territories. The toolkit is created through a collaborative process steered by WP5 Lead Partner TSR in which the partners share methods and approaches to define a specific IN-HABIT methodology. Each time the document is updated all partners will be duly informed about it. The present version is the first collection of tools deriving from the training process of the Local Community Activators

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and will be improved and adapted through the actual development of the project activities on the territory. Once the guidelines and tools are consolidated through contextual application in the IN-HUBS, the toolkit will be condensed in visual synthetic form for dissemination purposes.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

BOT	Book on a Tree LTD
BSC	Nodibinajums Baltic Studies Centre
B4B	Bridge for Billions SL
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
CPR	Common pool resources
CCPR	Co-created common pool resources
D	Deliverable
DFC	Design for Change España
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication, and Outreach
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EWB	Economic Well-being
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
HIDE	Hydepark Civic Association Triptych
HL	Healthy Lifestyle
H2020	Horizon 2020
IHW	Inclusive Health and Well-being
KLC	Key Local Contact
KII	Key Impact Indicators
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KQ	Kalniciema Quarter
ISIM	isIMPACT
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCA	Local Community Activator
LCREA	Lucca Crea SRL

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LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
MHWB	Mental health and Well-being
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
OT	Organisational Template
OC	Organisational Chart
PP	Project Partner
PPPPs	People-public-private partnerships
RPR	Rigas Planosanas Regions
SMSCs	Small and medium size cities
SUA	Slovenska Polnohospodarska Univerzita V NITRE
SWB	Social Well-being
T	Task
TSR	Tesseræ Urban Social Research – Colini-Tripodi GBR
UCO	Universidad de Córdoba
UNIPI	Università di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
VIS	Visionary and Integrated Solutions
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WTG	Wellness Telecom SL

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1. Introduction

Welcome!

If you are reading these pages you are probably a Local Community Activator in the IN-HABIT project or someone having a similar role in facilitating social engagement in complex projects. This Toolkit is aimed at territorial change-makers, helping them to find useful instruments and methods to steer local activities and engage stakeholders in wide people-public-private partnerships (PPPPs). These tools and methods are aimed at transforming places and behaviours through visionary solutions and inclusive processes. The Toolkit has a particular focus on gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion in promoting the health and well-being of inhabitants in the four cities of the H2020 IN-HABIT project. In the next pages, you find a set of guidelines assembled, with the contributions of transversal partners, specifically for the IN-HABIT project, which may be useful in other contexts too. The Toolkit includes tools, methods, and good practices specifically developed for the project or available in the public domains, and is aimed at improving the existing range of open educational and operative resources for the engagement of inhabitants in urban partnerships. Its components are at different stages of development, and are the result of the combined effort of different partners contributing from different disciplinary fields. Some are tools of general use and come with large documentation and manuals, some are prototypes designed for being experimented specifically for IN-HABIT, some others are just methodological recommendations that will require the design of specific tools. For this reason this is not a self contained document, that includes all the content available in offline format, it is rather a collection of summaries and links to extended documents and online resources that may be updated and perfected along the path.

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In the following, you find the **Glossary**, the **Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GDEI) Guidelines**, the **Management Objectives of the IN-HUBS**, their **Organisational Structure and Decision Making**, and a set of tools and templates that will support the LCAs in delivering the **Visionary Integrated Solution** to the territory. It includes how to set the local PPPPs coordination and to engage local stakeholders in the co-creation of innovative solutions, schemes for creating the **Local Communication Plans**, the **Inclusive Transformation Plans**, the **Inclusive Transition Paths** and other key tasks and deliveries foreseen by the project. Finally you find information about the **IN-HABIT Platform** and **IN-HABIT App** created by the project and the **Data Management** plan.

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2. Glossary

The IN-HABIT glossary defines a shared vocabulary among the partners of the H2020 IN-HABIT project. It facilitates both the internal communication and cooperation among the partners during the implementation, and the external communication of its objectives and actions towards a wider audience. The glossary is an essential instrument to outreach diverse social, professional and cultural groups through different language environments, and is also part of the [Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach plan \(DECO\)](#). The terms included in it have been mainly selected on the basis of the terminology employed by the submitted project description, completed with relevant terms that have emerged in the first phases of collaboration among the partners responsible for WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8, and consultation with the four cities (WP1-4).

The definitions proposed here aim to circumscribe clear, shared, operational meanings of these terms within the specific objectives and practices promoted by this project. The additional purpose is to facilitate correct translations of the main language of the project into the four local languages, and to support simple and inclusive formulations of its key concepts for general non-expert audiences. This glossary is meant as a co-created common pool resource of IN-HABIT.

The terms examined include:

- specific terminologies introduced by IN-HABIT methods and approaches;
- keywords widely used in EU policy and planning needing a clear explanation and communication to project participants;
- thematic keywords that have a specific relevance in disciplinary fields but may not be univocally recognised across different fields and to a general public;
- technical terms and acronyms.

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This document has been developed through a collaborative process involving the partners of WP5. All the partners have participated and contributed with their own interpretations, adding multiple perspectives from the various disciplines involved in the IN-HABIT project. The glossary in its entirety can be accessed [here](#).

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3. Gender, Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Guidelines

GDEI is a key aspect of the IN-HABIT project, that brings an essential attention to the fair distribution of health and well-being to everybody, and in particular to the strategies to reduce the gap for those at major risk of exclusion. The GDEI approach will be essential in all phases and tasks of the project, from the co-definition of impact indicators to the implementation of solutions on the ground.

What is GDEI? Some definitions of key terms and perspective

GDEI stands for Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion. **Gender** refers to the meaning that culture gives to biological differences ascribed to men and women at birth. Social construction (a concept from sociology and anthropology) states that our identities are shaped through the inculcation of values into children from birth in the family, education systems, mass media, etc. These are going to shape our behaviour and values along different dimensions of **diversity**, including class, race, age, gender, physical and mental ability, immigrant status, etc.

Identity relations are therefore different in different cultures, and they are not given by nature but socially constructed. Identity is not determined by biology, but by belonging to the social world, and the extent to which an identity is associated with negative perceptions has an important part in explaining the discrimination experienced by those who carry it. Exposure to bias toward one's group affects effort, self-confidence and productivity; therefore, designing organisations and activities to contrast these biases is key to achieving **equity and inclusion**.

GDEI and Innovation

Discrimination is a situation in which individuals with identical productive characteristics are treated differently from each other based on observable personal characteristics (such as age, ethnicity, gender, Body-Mass-Index, etc). This means that when discrimination occurs talent is systematically undervalued and both economic growth and innovation are hampered. This has

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been widely documented for all types of public and private organisations, for cities, and countries as a whole.

Viewing cities from a gender, diversity, equity and inclusion perspective requires an understanding of the main differences affecting the use of the urban space. Acknowledging that different groups have different needs and experiences in the urban space is the first step towards more user-sensitive and inclusive public services, and ultimately for more efficient ones.

How to work with a GDEI perspective in IN-HABIT?

- Assess your own knowledge of GDEI (see documents below) and use the WP6 support.
- Monitor **decision-making processes** across projects you are responsible for: how many people are involved? Who is at the table? (groupthink risk). How long do different people get to speak/contribute? Do more empowered participants practice active by-standing? What can you do to ensure all participants interact with a GDEI perspective?
- Monitor **participation and criteria** for projects you are responsible for: how are teams created? How are participants involved? Who is likely to be excluded? Can you select and evaluate anonymously? Do you provide sufficiently detailed and comparable feedback to everyone?
- Monitor **data collection systems, storage, and reporting**: use individuation and not generalisation, and check for involuntary use of stereotypes in reporting

To assess our own knowledge of GDEI the following documents can be consulted:

- [Guidelines for the collection of equality data](#)
- [Guidelines for use of gender inclusive language](#)
- [Gendered Innovations](#)

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- [LGBTI Equality Strategy](#)
- [EU Anti-Racism Action Plan](#)

Role of WP6 for the consortium

- Support partners in adopting best practices concerning GDEI at all stages of the project (participants involvement, co-design, co-deployment, reporting, etc.)
- Knowledge sharing with provision for all consortium of a short training on: “*Managing GDEI in Organisations: Key Principles and Applications*”, containing practical advice in using behavioural insights and practical tools including diversity recruitment, methods for reducing subjectivity and contrasting bias in groups, perspective training, inclusive communication to foster and advance GDEI.
- Collaboration at CLUSTER level with GDEI managers on sharing best practices and problem solving.

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4. Management Objectives of the IN-HUBs

The **IN-HUBs** are the organisational structures set by IN-HABIT in each of the four cities to steer the local project's activities. IN-HABIT's main objective is to:

“Promote Inclusive Health and Well-being (IHW) in peripheral SMSCs by mobilising local undervalued resources (culture and heritage, food, human animal bonds, environment and art) through visionary and integrated solutions (co-designed, co-developed and co-managed by local inhabitants and relevant stakeholders.”

This is accomplished through the essential role of specifically designed structures named IN-HUB. The IN-HUB is a laboratory of social innovation where people coming from different public and private organisations or as individual citizens work together for social change. It is a networking strategy for the enhancement of cooperation aimed at the co-design and co-management of spaces and a platform for structural dialogue and collaboration. IN-HUBs are both physical places for meeting and sharing and organisational structures to facilitate the transformative process.

IN-HUBs have the function to steer the local Private Public People Partnerships (PPPPs) to deliver visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) aimed at improving health and well-being in the selected areas of the IN-HABIT project. They have the key task of engaging local stakeholders and community representatives and developing inclusive and gender-balanced participation in the project-related activities. An essential role of the IN-HUB will be translating the methodological innovation proposed by the project's scientific partners into concrete actions in the selected territories.

Each IN-HUB is managed by a core group of professionals employed by the project partners, complemented by advisory boards and voluntary contributors. They will act in coordination with the project coordinator and the lead partners of the “transversal work packages” (WP5, 6, 7, 8). They will execute the key tasks required by the specific local WP (1-4) on the field. They

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will set up the People Private Public Partnerships (PPPPs) schemes created to deliver specific activities, and facilitate the engagement process of stakeholders, the co-design activity of VIS and their implementation with the scope of improving health and well-being in the selected territories. They will also have the task of reporting the actions, documenting the engagement process and acquiring essential data for impact assessment and scientific dissemination of solutions and good practices.

Figure 1. Working Packages' Structure

The IN-HUB may have a physical location into a designated community space in the area or rather distribute its activities through different existing community hubs or public spaces. The IN-HUB will also develop an essential digital dimension through public and restricted platforms, both to support the public communication of its activity and to perform archiving and data management for research purposes. Due to Covid-19 the virtual dimension may become dominant.

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The IN-HUBs are officially launched within the first year of the project, after the training of LCAs and the delivery of the Toolkit providing the common guidelines and tools for coordination. They will run until the end of the IN-HABIT partnership with a key role in steering, reporting, and disseminating the results and impacts of the PPPs actions on the territories and coordinating local activities within the general timeline of the project.

Annex 1 contains all the information regarding the tasks and deliverables of the pilot cities.

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5. IN-HUBs' Organisation and Decision Making

IN-HABIT through the IN-HUBs aims at experimenting with innovative forms of co-creation and decentralised governance. While its activities on the field are subject to learning by doing and processual adjustments, it is essential to track and develop a reflexive capacity about how the organisation and the decision-making process take shape and evolve in a shared and participatory manner during the project. For this reason, in this toolkit are included a few simple instruments to analyse and visualise how the activities of the IN-HUBs are organised in teams, who is taking responsibility for the main tasks and how decisions are taken and validated within the partnership. They have three main objectives: first, to establish internally a clear and agreed picture of how the partnership is supposed to work together; secondly, to facilitate the coordination with the activities of transversal work packages, facilitating thus the collaboration with the partners responsible for civic engagement, co-creation and impact assessment; thirdly, by recording useful information about how the IN-HUB model has been put in practice in local prototypes, to further evaluate innovations in decentralised governance.

5.1 Organisational Table (OT)

The OT is a simple template to report roles, tasks, decisional organs and procedures adopted in the IN-HUB to steer the PPPs. It details the main fields of activities of the IN-HUB with names and contacts of the responsible persons and organisations, and related forms of decision making adopted.

How does it work?

The table identifies four key activity fields of the IN-HUB - coordination, communication, co-design, implementation - plus any other relevant field of action defined by the team. For each of these fields it is identified who is involved at three different levels- the key persons responsible for making things happen, the project partners and the local stakeholders - and how decisions are taken.

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The local coordinators keep an updated version of the OT as agreed with the key members of the IN-HUB. Regular updates of the template should be done at project milestones, and the different version logs shared in the project repository with the project coordinator and WP leaders.

Who?

The Organisational Template is compiled by the local IN-HUB coordinator.

How to fill it out?

The aim of the template is to identify the key activities and functions carried by the IN-HUB organisational chart (section 5.2). When filling out the template, a series of questions and considerations can guide us in how to fill the categories of the template, which are represented in table 4. The template can be seen in table 5 and it can be downloaded from the common repository folder “*IN-HUBs Organizational Template*”, which can be accessed [here](#).

Key roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which are the roles and people in charge with specific responsibilities? - How are responsibilities attributed/shared within the team? - Which hierarchies are established to make actions happen?
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which PPs are responsible for the task, or for hiring the key roles? - Which other partners are engaged in taking decisions or implementing actions? - Who are the contact people for the partners?
Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who are the stakeholders involved in the actions?
Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are decisions about the general coordination and management of the PPPPs taken? - What kind of decision-making methods are adopted? - How frequent are meetings/assemblies/moments of verification? -How are decisions recorded, implemented, and monitored?

Table 1. Considerations for the Organizational Template.

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Organizational Template

What	Key roles	Partners	Stakeholders	Decision-making
Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local coordinator - LCA - Advisory board / steering groups - Other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners - International (transversal) partners - Local administration & departments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Stakeholder map - Key stakeholders - Missing or underrepresented actors - How to include issues of underrepresented groups 	
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication manager - Social media manager - Key local contacts (KLC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners - International (transversal) partners - Local administration & departments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selected audiences and target groups - Channels & media contacts 	
Co-design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LCA - Designers & technicians - Facilitators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Partners - International (transversal) partners - Local administration & departments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Targeted beneficiaries - Knowledge and service providers - Community leaders 	

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Implementation	- LCA - Local observers	- PP involved in the implementation of VIS on field - Local administration and departments - Private contractors and providers	- Providers - Contractors - Volunteers	
Impact Assessment	- WP7 Leader - LCA - Local observers			
Gender landscape / GDEI	- WP8 Leader			
(...any relevant function of the IN-HUB)				

Table 2. Organizational Template

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5.2 Organisational Chart (OC)

The OC is a visual complement to the organisational table, with the purpose to render visually and intuitively the organisational structure and the process done in the IN-HUBs. One suggestion is to draft this scheme as a zoom in the Stakeholder map template adopted by IN-HABIT (see section 7.2.1), focusing on the central part of the scheme that includes the project partners by detailing their connection with the local stakeholder ecosystem and their operative roles. However, drawing the organisation chart can be freely interpreted by the local teams using different styles and codes.

How does it work?

The same principles of the OT apply. The chart should be kept updated in line with the stakeholder mapping process, with periodic screenshots stored and shared in the project repository. Local language versions of the chart can be used for dissemination and outreach to the local stakeholders to support engagement and co-design and to stress the transparency of the process. There is a template ready to be edited on the platform Miro, which you can access [here](#).

An example of such a chart can be seen in figure 2. The OC was developed by the Nitra IN-HUB and it digs deeper in the stakeholder constellation by including not only the name of organizations, but also the individuals who are actively taking a role in the different tasks of the IN-HUB.

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Figure 2. Nitra's IN-HUB Organizational Chart

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6. Action Plan & Timelines

The IN-HABIT project has adopted a general action plan at the beginning of its activity, which is updated according to ordinary and exceptional occurrences. The [IN-HABIT Action Plan](#) details tasks, deliveries and milestones at the general project level and dictates how the IN-HUBs are supposed to coordinate their local activities within the general framework. In order to facilitate the coordination of the local IN-HUBs with the general development of the project, to avoid overlapping and conflict among different tasks for the LCAs, and to respect common milestones, the following set of instruments is provided.

6.1 Shared calendar

The shared calendar provides a practical instrument to coordinate tasks and roles in the project, visualising the execution of the actions and facilitating collaboration among the partners. We adopted the web-based list making application Trello to design our collaborative calendar. Key members of all partner organisations are invited as members with the faculty to edit the calendar. The board can be accessed [here](#).

The key events in the calendar will be reposted also in the visual timelines presented in the next paragraph.

6.2 Coordination Timelines

The project timelines aim to represent the succession of actions happening in the project in a visual and intuitive manner, facilitating the integration of the different actions at the local level and the coordination of the four PPPPs according to the general project milestones. During the training program of the LCAs a set of timelines has been created on a collaborative jamboard (Miro) used to facilitate the knowledge exchange among the partners. The five parallel timelines represent the general milestones and key events at the project level and the four sets of actions happening in the four local contexts.

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This interactive visualisation allows the core members of the IN-HUBs to keep track of the key steps of their PPPs, coordinate with the activities happening in the other partner cities, and visualise in a simple and intuitive way the advancements of the project. The board can be accessed [here](#).

How does it work?

Once that events and deliveries have been established within the IN-HUBs calendars, the LCA should update the common board on Miro with a simple post-it detailing the date, type of event, objectives, targets, WP, responsible persons, and links to any information published. Also, a link to the related Action template (see next paragraph) may be added. The timelines on Miro are for internal coordination scope, but simplified versions in the local language can be printed, published online, or shared as physical devices in the community hubs to communicate the advancement of the project in a friendly way.

Figure 3. Coordination Timelines.

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6.3 Local Action Template

The action template has the purpose to support the breaking-up of the action plan into clear, distinct, and feasible tasks, identifying the correct order of execution, those who are in charge of making them happen and all the partners and stakeholders that need to be involved in its accomplishment. It is also used for reporting issues experienced during the execution, problem-solving and to index all the produced outcomes and documentation.

How does it work?

The coordinators of the WPs according to the project implementation plan or local action plan identify discrete actions and tasks that need to be carried in the IN-HUB. The template is filled with all the required information. The timing of the action needs to be verified according to the project's GANTT chart and its connected milestones and deliverables. Then, a responsible person is contacted to agree on its delivery procedure and ultimately assigned to the task. The template is uploaded to the common repository and linked to the project timeline. It is completed in two rounds: in the first, the WP leader/coordinator details the task and the expected timing and procedures; in the second, the assigned person or team reports outcomes, issues and problem solving.

Format & language

Simple standard template filled in English. Local language versions can be produced within the IN-HUB to facilitate the internal organisation, but the main purpose is coordination at the project level and within transversal partners. The template must be filled in a short and synthetic way, more detailed descriptions and extensive reports may be attached or linked to it.

What to do with the complete entries?

The template with the initial description of tasks is shared by the WP coordinator with the responsible person in the IN-HUB and uploaded in the common repository.

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The template is later updated by the responsible person with comments about its realisation, issues and problem solving and complete with links and annexes to all documentation and reports produced about the task. The template can be seen in table 6 and it can be downloaded from the common repository folder “*IN-HUBs Action Template*”, which can be accessed [here](#).

IN-HUB Action Template

City IN-HUB:

What	Action/task identifier	When	Foreseen date or period for the task
Who	Person in charge for implementation/coordination	Who else	Partners/stakeholders involved
WP	Work package(s) to which the action contributes, responsible person for the lead partner	Delivery	Specific delivery or milestone
Purpose	Description of the key objective/scope of the action		
Type	Description of the type of action (event, presentation, workshop, social media post, survey, training, etc.)		
Outcomes	Describe the expected outcomes/achievements of the action		
Organisation	Describe the different steps and tasks necessary to deliver the action in a correct order, including needed skills, resources and equipment. Detail responsible persons for subtasks if needed.		
Target	Direct beneficiaries or target groups of the action		
Communication	Specific communication channels and actions to be employed to carry out and disseminate the activity		

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Issues	Difficulties affecting the delivery of the task and related problem solving
Notes	Any other information that is useful to complete, report or evaluate the action
Documentation	Links to annexed reports and documentation materials about the action, pictures etc.

Table 3. IN-HUB Action Template

6.4 Integration Assessment Grid

The Integration Assessment Grid is an exercise which helps verify and self-assess the state of the art of your plans and its integrated approach in all dimensions. From the very nature of the collaboration that IN-HABIT aims to create in the form of Public-Private-People Partnerships (PPPPs), every plan is integrated at different levels and the actions need to be synergically thought to deliver the plans' objective in practice.

The principle of integration applied to urban development comprises five key dimensions: **horizontal** (among local stakeholders), **vertical** (government tiers), **territorial** (neighbouring municipalities and districts within functional areas), **policy sector** (social, economic, environmental, etc), and between **hard/soft measures**.

This tool is useful in all phases of collective planning, from the co-development of the Inclusive Transformation Plan (ITPlan) at month 18 (as it will be later presented in chapter 11), to the co-implementation phase. The Integration Assessment Grid is also useful to report difficulties, solutions, inspirations, and innovative elements of the engagement process of local stakeholders and communities.

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How does it work?

As part of IN-HABIT, Local Community Activators (LCAs) have received an introduction to the integrated approach and the application of the Integration Assessment Grid. We encourage the use of this grid together with the members of the local partnership at best, and if possible.

For each item in the left column of the grid, you are asked to fill two types of information: (1) how much your ITPlan is integrated and on which aspect, and (2) what measures or actions can be done in order to advance in the integration of your plan.

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Integration Assessment Grid Template

Types of integration	Description	What is the current situation of your ITPlan?	To what extent can progress be made?
Policy/sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of economic, social, and environmental challenges • Join up solutions and minimise the effects of negative externalities 		
Horizontal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop partnerships at local level • Bring together all the main actors around a challenge 		
Vertical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align policies, interventions, and funding upwards • Vertical chain of governance • Ensure coherence and build scale 		

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Territorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure cooperation takes place between adjacent municipalities in functional urban areas • Minimise edge effects and displacement problems 		
Hard and soft investments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate physical investments with human resources in urban regeneration • For instance, European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) + European Social Fund (ESF) • Avoid silos 		

Table 4. Integration Matrix Template

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7. Engagement process

7.1 Inclusion of vulnerable citizens in health and well-being research

Strategies, tools, and methods

To prevent growing health and well-being related inequalities (people affected by multiple level of deprivation and marginality, living in poverty, people at risk of exclusion or discrimination for their ethnic background, religion, gender, age or mental & physical health issues) is central to the scope of IN-HABIT. While IN-HABIT calls for co-producing in the decision-making processes, the involvement of people suffering from the consequences of unjust contemporary society might prove difficult for a number of reasons: time, money, lack of trust and confidence, scepticism towards institutions. Unfamiliarity with co-design might limit citizens' confidence to share their opinions and reinforce citizens' disbelief that their views will be heard and acted upon. Moreover, residents' priorities should be taken into account: food, jobs, security of housing, education and primary needs might be more pressing than any research-led interview, meeting or activity. Part of the co-creation process should be also to transform research and action, defining together the "problem setting", namely identifying the most pressing issue with the people most concerned. Consequently, the final agenda for the participatory process is co-designed in a way that welcomes the input from residents and project promoters. The research project might be an opportunity to voice unheard demands, offer a creative frame to think collectively and organise for co-deploying solutions.

This section of the Toolkit offers strategies, tools, and methods aimed to improve the capacities to foster democratic participation and an ethical approach to research on health and well-being with and about specific target groups according to few key principles:

First and foremost, people affected by multiple levels of deprivation are different and ad-hoc strategies and methods for engagement should be accordingly devised to protect, shield and enable the most vulnerable to speak and share ideas and concerns in a safe space. Second, the

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deployment of the strategies is context dependent. Third, the researcher (in IN-HABIT, the LCA) is not neutral and independent from context, and the approach chosen is also part of the research: researchers should encourage and value diverse perspectives, be mindful of different powers, not rushing for consensus based solutions, while adapting to (unwritten) 'rules' of interactions in the new environment. Fourth, the ethic of the involvement process demands that the project results are community driven and not instrumental to the completion of the research. Five, every information collected from the target group, decision made (and not upon them but with them), and implementation should be transparent, based on the commitment to share, inform and return for scrutiny to those who inhabit the space.

Assuming that baseline research on the condition, contextual socio, economic, environmental research is premiered in the target area chosen by the project, the following steps are suggested:

- LCA should spend time in the target area, establishing collaboration with experienced and key community based organisations, associations and leading figures being aware of local pre-existing potential conflicts. Contacting local schools is essential to reach out to families through their kids, attend community centres and meeting places and exercise participatory observation.
- Inform, communicate and collect data in multiple languages that are accessible to the majority of people in both analog and digital forms.
- Chain of acquaintances, word-of-mouth recruitment through friends, families, volunteers, community organise, or a trusted person which may act as bridge, are preferable to reach out to people unfamiliar with co-design.
- Set limits to confidentiality and occasions where this may occur.
- Participating in an event or meeting has costs attached (busy life/working schedules, child care, transportation costs, and other families or personal restrictions) which could prevent or hinder citizens living in vulnerable circumstances from participating. In specific cases various incentives and compensation might be an option (as it will be done for example with the behavioural games).

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- Set strict deadlines which limit time-spending in order to build trust, lessen the burden; also, organising events back to back with other compatible activities
- Easily accessible and familiar locations might help to organise a meeting. In some cases, also different and unusual locations might improve the feeling of trust and safety.
- Offer low budgets, easily accessible activities which are appropriate to different ages and types of groups, e.g. digital storytelling and photo-voice, storyboards, convivial gatherings, theatre-related activities, or an unstructured dialogue etc.
- To meet gender-related concerns, gender-specific meetings and encounters should be considered (see chapter 3)

Throughout the whole engagement process, the facilitators should bear in mind the question “what are the benefits for the participants and the whole community? ” in order to make sure that involvement is worthwhile. Since the beginning of the activities, facilitators need to have a clear idea of which benefit can be granted to the participants having in mind a clear and transparent management of the expectations.

A key element for the engagement of the local community is the stakeholder mapping process. A stakeholder map is a tool that supports the development of an inclusive transformation process from the initial survey to the evaluation of final impacts and future sustainability of the project. It is a visualisation of all the stakeholders involved or supposed to be involved, as well as all the relevant formal or informal subjects that have a relation with the project. This map should support the creation and management of the local PPPs, tracking the evolution of the partnership during the project time, and highlighting the engagement process of groups at risk of exclusion. It is a living document, representing the evolution of the social interaction in any phase and will be subject to periodical updates, producing “screenshots” at given moments to compare the progress of the local partnerships in relation with the general IN-HABIT project milestones. We start from the focused list of organisations and actors directly involved in the IN-HABIT project but ideally should extend into representing comprehensively the social innovation ecosystem of each city and to highlight to what extent the project becomes embedded in the local socio-economic reality. The key purpose of the map is for internal use,

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but partial versions of the stakeholder maps can be published online, printed in brochures, or posted in community hubs as part of the engagement and dissemination activities of the project. The stakeholder map in IN-HABIT constitutes the core element of the ITPath, the specific tool for steering and monitoring the inclusive engagement of stakeholders experimented by the project. (see chapter 12)

7.2 Engagement tools

In the following, a set of tools dedicated to map the stakeholder ecosystem condensing around the project, analyse their (potential) role and interests, identify missing and vulnerable groups, and devise strategies for their engagement.

7.2.1 Stakeholder Target Template

For the IN-HABIT stakeholder mapping process the Stakeholder Target Template has been adopted. Based on the 4 helix model of social innovation, it is derived from similar models experimented for years by the URBACT Networks.

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Figure 4. Stakeholder target Template.

The target diagram presents the four main fields/typologies of territorial stakeholders according to their legal status as public, private, research or social actors. Stakeholders must be positioned in one of the four fields on the ground of how they act, rather than how they are formally / informally constituted as subjects having a stake in the local context.

The three concentric rings define four fields that are used to position the stakeholders according to the degree of involvement in the project. The closer to the center is the core group of project partners steering the process. The second ring includes stakeholders directly engaged in or affected by the project (primary stakeholders). The third is for stakeholders indirectly or partially affected by the project activities and impacts (secondary stakeholders). The external area is used either to map missing stakeholders that should/may be reached out for engagement or that act at a different territorial scale but may be relevant in the process (national institutions or transnational networks, global media, etc.)

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How does it work?

The map is created collaboratively using an online board, which allows all the invited members of the IN-HUB to keep it updated with the evolution of the partnership. It is used to collect basic information such as name, logo, typology, legal form and operative connections of each stakeholder. It includes all the needed links to navigate publicly available information about the different actors. The main language of the map should be English, summarising key information about the local stakeholders for research comparison purposes, but it can also include info and links to documents or web pages in local language when the English version is not available. Regular screenshots of the map should be produced and stored at the milestones of the project. The board can be accessed [here](#).

How to produce stakeholders map entries?

Every time a stakeholder is involved or identified to be involved in the project a new entry on the map should be created. The collection of the data is done directly on the shared Miro board, but also a simple spreadsheet collecting the key info of each stakeholder should be used.

This spreadsheet should be filled and stored by the IN-HUBs to create a separate database of key stakeholders of each PPPP.

Data and publication

The information that is stored on the collaborative board must be of public use, already available online on official websites or social media while personal data and contacts should be avoided. The stakeholder map should work as an aggregator of existing information and public interfaces. It would be a good practice also to inform all the stakeholders that they have been included in the map, what is its purpose and what will be the audience and ask for their feedback and revisions of the collected information. Personal data and contacts may be added to a separate database which should be then stored and managed according to the general rules set by the general [DMP](#).

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An example of the development of a stakeholder map can be seen in figures 5 and 6. These two examples capture two moments of Cordoba's IN-HUB stakeholder mapping process, which actively shaped the attempt to include the “missing stakeholders”.

Figure 5. First Moment of Cordoba's IN-HUB Stakeholder Map.

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Figure 6. Second Moment of Cordoba's IN-HUB Stakeholder Map.

7.2.2 Stakeholder Analysis Template

The Stakeholder Analysis Template is used to assess interests, potential contributions and engagement strategies of the key stakeholders. The model proposed here is a basic suggestion, inspired by the methods disseminated by [URBACT](#), but it can be adapted according to specific aims and moments of the process.

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How does it work?

The stakeholders are selected and compared according to how they are potentially affected by the project, what kind of contribution or competence they can bring in and what advantage they can get out of the involvement. A field is dedicated to pinpoint possible strategies to better engage them. According to the purpose of the analysis, it can be useful to distinguish between primary and secondary stakeholders: primary are those more concerned with the challenge, or affected by the actions; secondary those concerned but might not feel directly involved. This exercise can be part of the planning and management activity, but also proposed during public events for outreach and co-design purposes.

Secondary Stakeholder	INTEREST (How is it affected?)	MOTIVATION (What can they get out?)	RESOURCES (What can they bring in?)	Actions to address stakeholder engagement
Primary Stakeholder	INTEREST (How is it affected?)	MOTIVATION (What can they get out?)	RESOURCES (What can they bring in?)	Actions to address stakeholder engagement

Table 5. Stakeholder Analysis Template.

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7.2.3 Engagement Diaries

The purpose of the Engagement Diaries is that of recording the progress of the IN-HABIT project from the perspective of LCAs, reporting difficulties, solutions, inspirations, and innovative elements of the engagement process of local stakeholders and communities.

How does it work?

One entry every 2/3 months (at least) should be produced by LCAs or other members of the IN-HUB. It may be the same person in charge of the whole diary, or shifting persons according to the different tasks and moments of the process, or even a collective narration. Also, key stakeholders could be involved in providing their accounts in a particular perspective or moment. What is important is that it is clear in every diary entry who is speaking and whose feelings and experiences are communicated. This is not meant to be an impersonal, “objective” report but a personal, situated and contextual account of a process of exchange between people. Entries can be produced after key events or official milestones, but also to document moments of unexpected difficulties and to accompany problem-solving and the search for innovative solutions.

Format & language

The diary entries can be recorded as text but also as slide presentations, short podcasts, interviews, visual mind maps, VOX Pops or videos. Participants are free to choose the format that works best for them. Entries can be in their language. Their format should be discussed and agreed by the team as part of the Local Communication Strategy and plan and used for publication on the website and through social media.

Length

Entries do not need to be long, they can be a short-written paragraph or a quick interview, they need to capture the key point / difficulty / solution and transmit it to a general public with a clear and synthetic style.

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What to do with the complete entries?

Once diarists have completed their diary entries, IN-HUBs Coordinators need to do three things:

- If needed translate written material into English and add subtitles to any video entries;
- Share with the WP5 lead Partner TSR and Communication officers and upload the entry onto the general [project repository](#);
- Be prepared to discuss how the material can be utilised for wider outputs, including the general website or social media posts

Content of the Diary entry

Each entry should answer to four key-questions:

- What activities of stakeholders/community engagement have been carried?
- What strategies have been adopted to include groups at risk of exclusion?
- What difficulties have been experienced in developing the planned actions and which solutions have been deployed?
- What was the added value of applying IN-HABIT approach and methods, and what are the key learnings?

To facilitate the scripting of the diary entry the following template can be used, although not mandatory. It refers to the [framework for change](#) introduced during the training for assessing key fields of action, variables and moments of the process.

In order to fill it out, it can be downloaded from the common repository folder “*IN-HUBs Engagement Diaries*”, which can be accessed [here](#).

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Diary Scripting Template

IN-HUB, City:		Diary maker:	
Date		Activity period:	

Title of the entry	
Logline	(one sentence summarising the key activity or point)

Field/dimension (Tick or describe the main dimension of the activity)

	Social (people)	
	Spatial (places)	
	Objectives (strategic)	
	Practices (making)	

Variables

	Language	Main issues in terms of translation between different natural languages or expert formalisations vs. Common language; adopted approaches for inclusion, communication, dissemination.
	Procedures	Essential procedures to deliver the actions and engage sensible groups
	Expectations	Expected results and prospects for managing participants expectations
	Time	Essential timing and milestones of the actions

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Moment

Indicate which of the eight key moments of the process this action is related to; quote also what other moments/activities have been essential to the preparation.

Figure 7. Moments of a transformative process.

Key questions:

- Describe the activity of engaging local stakeholders/community in the action carried during the selected period.
- Describe the strategies adopted to include the larger group of stakeholders and in particular those at risk of exclusion with a GDEI perspective.
- Describe difficulties experienced in developing the planned actions and the adopted solutions.
- Describe the added value of applying the IN-HABIT approach and methods in the specific context and key learnings deriving from the action.

Annexes

Pictures, drawings and any other documents useful to document the event and prepare the final elaboration of the entry.

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Once filled and checked that we have answers for all the key-questions, the form of the storytelling can be readapted to the preferred narrative style, i.e a journalistic text, a short video, a podcast or a slide presentation.

7.3 Measuring engagement

According to the KPIs defined in IN-HABIT’s project proposal, there is a minimum threshold of people who are expected to participate in the Public-Private-People Partnerships (PPPPs) of each city. These numbers can be seen in the following table.

KPIs	Target value			
	Cordoba	Riga	Lucca	Nitra
Number of decision makers and urban planners that enhance their skills for IHW planning	20	20	15	30
Number of male and female vulnerable people involved in IN-HUBs	50	30	25	40
Number of companies involved in IN-HUBs	20	20	10	10
Number of male and female young people involved in initiatives developed to foster IHW	300	200	250	250
Number of male and female local champions promoting mindset changes	12	5	5	15
Number of business developed by or employing male and female vulnerable people	5	3	2	2
Number of women leaders involved in initiatives developed by IN-HABIT	10	5	5	7

Table 6. KPIs to evaluate the PPPPs (selection)

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These numbers were a first estimation in the IN-HABIT project proposal to quantify the participants to the Private-Public-People Partnership (PPPP). The PPPP is based on IN-HABIT's approach, and it is meant to be an ever-evolving ecosystem of stakeholders, with a balanced representation of all groups. The four quadrants of the stakeholder mapping template in section 7.2.1 reflect the four (and five) innovation model helix, as shown in figure 8. In order to establish a healthy stakeholder ecosystem, it will be important not only to guarantee a minimum threshold of participants, but a balanced distribution of stakeholders belonging to one (or more) of the four key sectors. In other words, it will be essential to ensure the presence of people (civil servants, elected representatives et al) representing the public interest, experts and researchers bringing advanced knowledge, entrepreneurs developing economic potential and citizens voicing not only the needs but also the resources of the territory.

Figure 8. Five Helix model in the IN-HABIT approach

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The IN-HUB needs to accommodate diversity of opinions, collaboration between potentially conflicting visions, action planning and decision-making, all of which require different formats, tools, as well as spaces, dedication and time for it to succeed in the objective of fostering collaboration between actors in the governance of co-created common pool resources (CCPR).

Therefore, not all actors will be addressed through the same means or will be dedicated the same time and attention (e.g. a short meeting with a thematic expert vs. longer and recurrent events to promote the empowerment of the most vulnerable groups). In the same way, the IN-HUB should not aim to engage a fixed number of “vulnerable people”, but rather to put the focus on representing adequately the needs and demands of the different interest groups and individuals, while giving the chance to those at risk of exclusion to assume responsibility roles and exercise their democratic engagement. In other terms, it is not only the numbers but also the quality of the engagement that is mainly capable of guaranteeing a positive impact.

As discussed in the previous sections, the stakeholder mapping and analysis will be fundamental in order to measure the engagement process in a qualitative and quantitative manner; it provides an overview of the number of stakeholders (identified and outreached), their interests/thematic focus, and their level of engagement and capacities.

Moreover, IN-HUB should be understood not only as indicating the governing and steering body of the activities -which for practical reasons will probably not exceed circa 10 people- but as a wider term encompassing all outreach activities that will take place during the co-design, co-deployment and co-management phases of the project.

In this sense, we propose, as examples, a series of activities that could take place during the engagement process and the estimated number of people participating in them. This can be understood as guidelines to tailor the engagement process to the local context, counting on LCA to select the most appropriate mode and size for the activity.

While it is difficult to prescribe exact thresholds of participants to the activities the LCAs can choose the best form of participatory activity to better engage stakeholders as well the greater inclusion of the subjects more vulnerable or at risk of exclusion.

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Size	N° of participants	Type	Expected results
P2P	2- 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bilateral meetings with representatives of target groups • Partners coordination • Institutional briefs 	Operational agreements, contractual agreements, survey on converging interests, consultation and expertise provision
SMALL	10-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacitation workshops • Mindset change workshops • Action planning workshops • Integration assessment grid exercise • Decision-making in IN-HUB's core group • Regular working groups • Focus groups 	Co-design, co-management, co-deployment, outreach, expectations management
MEDIUM	15-50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design workshops • Interactive walks • Integration assessment grid 	Visioning, assessment, consultation, outreach, co-monitoring
BIG	> 50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thread mapping • Public/moderated discussions • World café • Community surveys 	Public relations and communication, co-monitoring, consultation, assessment,

Table 7. Example of engagement activities and their outreach capacity.

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8. IHW impact assessment of VIS with a GDEI perspective

As a general objective, the proposed evaluation action aims at revealing and isolating the results of IN-HABIT solutions on mental health, socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles of the target groups in the 4 pilot cities.

8.1 What do we assess?

Figure 9. Assessment process

TRANSVERSAL EVALUATION QUESTIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and to what extent people's health and well-being has improved thanks to the IN-HABIT solutions? - Does the impact show any significant difference among the groups at risk of discrimination in each city? - Which is the impact on each group at risk of discrimination compared to the rest of the target inhabitants? - Which component of the innovation (social, cultural, nature-based and digital) has produced the most significant changes on people's health and well-being? - Which sub-dimensions of health and well-being have been most affected by the solutions? - How and to what extent the results of the project have been influenced by the Covid-19 pandemic?

Table 8. Transversal Evaluation Questions

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Theoretical approach

The conceptual principles underpinning ISIM theoretical approach and derived by the literature review are as follows: 1. Health and well-being are strongly interlinked; 2. Health and well-being are influenced by the social, economic and environmental context; 3. The perception of the resources and opportunities provided by the city as well as the perception of freedom and equality in accessing these resources and opportunities, have an impact on individuals' health and well-being; 4. The subjective experience of health and well-being plays a pivotal role in the impact assessment; 5. Assessing well-being requires a holistic approach

Figure 10. Process for the development of Inclusive Health and Well-being Indicators.

Identification of Dimensions and sub-dimension of Health and Well-being

The rationale for the choice of the IHW sub-dimensions is based on the type of solutions envisaged by the IN-HABIT project in each pilot city; and the research perspective that considers humans as social and cultural animals living in an urban context but in need for stronger bonds with local resources, more specifically: nature/green spaces, animals, cultural life and healthy food. According to the health and well-being definitions based on international and European organizations (e.g. WHO, OECD, EU) and literature, 4 main dimensions have been identified: Social Well-being (SWB), Healthy Lifestyle (HL), Economic Well-being (EW), Mental health (MH).

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Figure 12. Sub-dimensions of SWB.

Figure 13. Sub-dimensions of HL.

Figure 14. Sub-dimensions of EWB.

Figure 15. Sub-dimensions of MHWB.

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Identification of IHW indicators

For each sub-dimension, a first set of IHW Indicators have been selected and proposed by ISIM: some of the proposed indicators have been derived and adapted from existing assessment frameworks and metrics, mainly from OECD, WHO, Eurofound and Eurostat indicators; others have been proposed by partner ISIM as new IN-HABIT specific indicators. This first set of preliminary indicators has been further validated and integrated by the feedback received from city partners and inhabitants during the co-design phase.

Identification of GDEI indicators

GDEI characteristics which may affect the project's impact on health and well-being are included in the research framework and quantitative data are disaggregated accordingly. Expected results and IHW Indicators which may be influenced by GDEI characteristics are included in the research framework, which are selected with the involvement of the representatives of the groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion. People at risk of discrimination and exclusion are involved from the beginning in the co-design of indicators as well as in the data collection actions. Specific attention is paid to those incentives and actions that may ensure an equitable participation of persons at risk of discrimination and exclusion in the research activities, thanks to the involvement of local observers as linguistic and cultural mediators. For each sub-dimension, a first set of IHW Indicators have been selected and proposed by ISIM: some of the proposed indicators have been derived and adapted from existing assessment frameworks and metrics, mainly from OECD, WHO, Eurofound and Eurostat indicators; others have been proposed by partner ISIM as new IN-HABIT specific indicators. This first set of preliminary indicators has been further validated and integrated by the feedback received from city partners and inhabitants during the co-design phase.

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Figure 15. Process for the identification of GDEI personal characteristics.

Figure 16. GDEI perspective's influence on the evaluation plan.

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Within the proposed impact evaluation, intersectionalities among the selected characteristics (age, gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, citizenship status, migrant legal status, country of birth, importance of religion in one’s life, religion, disability, type of disability) will be also considered, by capturing changes on health and well-being over groups who hold multiple GDEI characteristics.

The key findings from the literature review, as well as those from the consultation of gender and diversity oriented organizations at local level (workshops, questionnaires and interviews) have allowed the identification of IHW sub-dimensions that are sensitive to GDEI personal characteristics of interest. Each IHW sub-dimension includes a set of GDEI indicators.

IHW sub-dimensions that are GDEI sensitive have then been identified for each of the main personal characteristics.

IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to age	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to sexual orientation	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to gender	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to disability	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to ethnicity and religion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial well-being - Safety - Social inclusion - Social cohesion - Housing - Financial situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discrimination - Security and violence - Social cohesion - Employment - Cultural participation - Leisure and free time - Housing - Financial situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security and violence - Discrimination - Employment - Spatial well-being - Leisure and free time - Job and skill satisfaction - Financial situation - Housing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social inclusion - Social cohesion - Spatial well-being - Employment - Financial situation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social inclusion - Social cohesion - Discrimination - Equality - Cultural participation - Leisure and free time

Table 9. IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to GDEI.

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Co-design process

The subjective indicators on socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles have been selected by means of a co-design process where the theoretical and empirical assumptions of the researchers have been integrated with the view of the local inhabitants and representatives of local organizations on the expected changes on people's health and well-being which may be, at least in part, attributable to the solutions envisaged in the 4 pilot cities. The perspective of people with personal characteristics related to GDEI has been considered by involving them in two moments of the process, namely the co-design workshops with inhabitants and the survey addressed to the representatives of GDEI organizations.

Phase 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Literature review and first partners consultations
Phase 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Inhabitants' consultations
Phase 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Establishment of the city value chains

Table 10. Phases in the co-design process of IHW indicators

The outputs of co-design workshops and partners contribution have been analysed and integrated into the impact assessment framework, which is based on 4 city specific "value chains" articulated in the following elements: context and solutions; city target groups; expected changes from partners' perspective and expected changes from local inhabitants' perspective.

Based on the Theory of change approach, the empiric definition of the city specific IHW indicators has been guided by this participatory approach, where the perspective of the researchers on health and well-being has been integrated with the expected changes perceived by local inhabitants.

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A set of specific evaluation questions have been formulated:

CORDOBA	LUCCA	NITRA	RIGA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and to what extent culture and heritage-related solutions have improved the health and well-being of local target groups? - What subdimensions of health and well-being have been most affected by culture-related solutions? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and to what extent human-animal bonds solutions have improved the health and well-being of local target groups? - What subdimensions of health and well-being have been most affected by human-animal solutions? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and to what extent art and nature-based solutions have improved the health and well-being of local target groups? - What subdimensions of health and well-being have been most affected by arte and nature-based solutions? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How and to what extent food-related solutions have improved the health and well-being of local target groups? - What subdimensions of health and well-being have been most affected by food-related solutions?

Table 11. City specific questions related to VIS.

The proposed IHW Indicators, resulting from the co-design, have been grouped in 4 meta-categories.

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Figure 17. Categories for the IHW Indicators.

8.2 How do we assess the IHW impact of VIS?

The IN-HABIT impact assessment is based on an inclusive “mixed methodology” research (Amaturo, Punziano, 2016) using qualitative/quantitative methods of data collection and analysis. The impact assessment is also based on the “practical participatory evaluation” (P-PE) research framework (J. B. Cousins and E. Whitmore, 1998), which is focused on stakeholders’ participation in the evaluation process in order to increase the evaluation's relevance, ownership, and thus use.

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The evaluation process will include three steps of data collection (by city partners), and analysis (by ISIM and UREAD): 1 Ex-ante evaluation; 2 Ongoing evaluation; 3 ex-post evaluation.

ISIM has adopted the “Bricolage” approach to impact assessment (Nicholls 2009), consisting of a combination of 3 types of evaluation approaches (the Theory Based Evaluation, The Realistic Evaluation, the Developmental Evaluation, or Evaluation that promotes development) which seems appropriate to the specific case of a research that aims to bring out the changes (positive, negative, expected or unexpected) made by a project of a complex type (Rogers, 2009), such as that of IN-HABIT, implemented in a generalized situation of uncertainty (related to the diversity of social contexts) and modulated with respect to different types of stakeholders’ needs and expectations.

Citizen science inclusion mechanism

Within the impact assessment strategy, a Citizen Science Inclusion Mechanism (CSIM) has been designed to define and represent the various levels and types of contributions provided by local inhabitants to the impact assessment activities in each pilot city. The CSIM is articulated into 4 levels. Each level is interconnected with the previous and the following level and differs from the others on the basis of the degree of involvement in the research activities (level 1 represents the highest degree of involvement and level 4 the lowest), as well as on the basis of the type of contribution provided by inhabitants.

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Figure 18. Citizen Science Inclusion Mechanism and its four levels of engagement.

Assessment tools

The impact assessment of IN-HABIT's VIS will be made by using four quantitative and five qualitative tools. Qualitative tools will allow ISIM to integrate quantitative data and to go deep in the data analysis.

Tool	Definition/features	Use in impact assessment
Quantitative		
Survey	It consists of questions related to IHW indicators' sub-dimensions which will be administered mainly through an on-line form, using Microsoft Forms, it will allow the collection of responses while ensuring the anonymity of the respondents and the collection of data matrices that will then be subjected to statistical analysis exclusively in	Collecting primary data on health and socio-economic well-being among people living or attending the 4 intervention city areas.

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	<p>aggregate form for evaluation purposes.</p> <p><i>Instructions on how to plan and manage the survey are included in the “Baseline Study Guidelines for LCAs”. One for each city: Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga</i></p>	
Secondary data collection	<p>Through administrative data and available statistics on the basis of the following dimensions: Demography; Socio-Economic Well-Being; Attitudes; Participation; Poverty And Income; Housing; Education; Employment; Crime, Discrimination And Violence; Consumption; Time Use; Health; Health Determinants; Mobility; Mental Health</p> <p><i>Instructions for city partners on how to collect the data with a GDEI perspective, are included in the “Methodological note for cities on secondary data collection on inclusive health and wellbeing” developed with UREAD</i></p>	<p>Analysing the 4 city context with the twofold aim of (i) better interpretation of the IN-HABIT results and (ii) discounting external factors who may have contributed to the changes affecting inhabitants' IHW.</p>
Gamified survey	<p>It implies a mission or a challenge for the user who is asked to provide data and accomplish a task in exchange for a reward. It will be deployed through the IN-HABIT App developed by BOT</p>	<p>Collecting data provided by the users (local inhabitants) on a voluntary basis.</p>
Mobile experience sampling method	<p>It implies the collection of data several times during the day of the users in relation to their experience of the urban space. It will be deployed through the IN-HABIT App</p>	<p>Collecting data provided by the users (local inhabitants) on a voluntary basis.</p>
Qualitative		

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<p>Co-design workshops</p>	<p>ISIM has developed a guidelines scheme aimed at: identifying the expected results and possible changes that IN-HABIT can produce on health and well-being of the citizens; Identifying the most relevant dimensions of health and well-being according to the citizens; Identified aspects of health, well-being and lifestyles which are more dependent from Covid-19 (Q8). <i>Instructions on how to manage the co-design workshop are included in the “Workshop guidelines” for LCAs.</i></p>	<p>Detecting citizens perspective on inclusive health and well-being dimensions and sub-dimensions</p>
<p>Focus groups</p>	<p>It will be conducted once a year from year 1 using the methodology of "case studies" (Robert Yin 2003) that requires the use of qualitative social research techniques aimed at investigating, through the observation of “privileged witnesses”, the changes generated by the project on specific groups of inhabitants. <i>Instructions on how to plan and run the focus group are included in the “Baseline Study Guidelines for LCAs”. One for each city: Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga</i></p>	<p>Investigating, especially in the ongoing evaluation phase, some indicators that concern the sub dimensions of well-being by virtue of the complexity of the cognitive object such as, for example the Sub dimension of Social cohesion concerning the aspects of feeling of trust in community relations, the perception of accessibility to the resources offered by the local community etc</p>
<p>Semi-structured interviews</p>	<p>They are used in this evaluation plan with particular attention to the selection phase of the interviewees in order to mitigate the selection bias known in the literature for which they are identified as interviewees of individuals who are lateral to the organizations themselves.</p>	<p>Collecting data on specific qualitative indicators on socio-economic well-being. Interviews will be used: to complement the focus groups (or replace them in case of Covid-19 restrictions); for storytelling purposes.</p>

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<p>Storytelling</p>	<p>Through a five-steps methodology to use storytelling as a means of evaluation: preparation of the story; identification of the protagonist, identification of the triggering event, description of a process of change and evolution, future evolution</p> <p><i>Instructions on how to use storytelling for impact assessment are included in the “Baseline Study Guidelines for LCAs”. One for each city: Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga</i></p>	<p>In addition to quantitative analysis: grasping emotional aspects and nuances on individual experiences; rebuilding the changes that happen in a very short time (even a day) in a longer time beyond the project; detecting unexpected changes and aspects of the context, not considered in the research design</p>
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Table 12. Assessment tools explanation and use.

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9. Local Communication Plan

This section represents a brief how-to guide to start and manage Dissemination and Communication actions into local contexts involved in the IN-HABIT project.

A more detailed document - Dissemination and Communication (DC) Plan - about the comprehensive [Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach \(DECO\)](#) strategy of the project is available. This document includes all the guidelines and actions related to the IN-HABIT project objectives, as well as an overview of the various communication strategies, messages and expected key performance indicators (KPIs)

The Local Communication Plan consists in defining the actions and channels that will allow the project to:

- Be visible to citizens, stakeholders and the press.
- Collect the support of the locals to the project, the support and capacity for impact.
- Extend the experience to areas or groups less sensitive to IN-HABIT issues.
- Bring the local experience to a broader level of institutional communication, determining present and future choices, local and other cities, which have as objectives and values those pursued by IN-HABIT.
- Create a local and global relational heritage of great added value that supports the progress and development of the project.
- Create an informative heritage of the project in its local dimension (given by research data, experiences, research, empirical evidence, insights into the local values and socio-cultural dimensions and their evolution, the gender landscape and health and well-being inequality).
- Help citizens understand how to better experience urban space through the most direct form of communication: living experiences.
- Encourage citizens to share information and experiences.

The main to-dos planned locally, in the next few months, will concern:

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- A first moment of information for local media and institutional stakeholders that will contextualize the start of local activities in each of the cities within the overall framework of the project, defining purposes, values, promoters, and scientific starting points **(press launch Oct. 2021)**
- Additional launch moments dedicated to the promotion of interventions in the contexts of individual cities, which will aim to inform on local paths and initiate a process of sharing and local involvement, which will take place with the launches of city hubs **(Oct. 2021- May 2022)**
- A subsequent stream of information that will be based on the story of the evolution of each project at the local level and the return of local experience for the locals and a wider audience and which will also support the goal of local engagement
- The contextualization of storytelling on the advancement of the local experience with useful research data in accompanying them, setting up a at a strategic, effective and communication
- Subsequent moments of dissemination of research data on local experiences with dissemination purposes and aimed at encouraging the replicability of the project in different areas of the world.
- Continuous contact with the media and with institutions aimed at increasing the visibility of the project more and more locally and beyond

The actions of the local communication plan are defined in a general plan and carried out under the guidance of the WP8 leader, BOT, who, during the project, will take care of informing the Key local Contacts, the communication contacts of the partners and the PPs regarding the campaigns in the planning, to the timing of each one, providing to support the operations with daily indications and dedicated training moments.

Website

One of the main goals of the IN-HABIT website is to reach the local audience in the four cities and to inform about actions and initiatives that will take place in Cordoba, Nitra, Riga and Lucca. In order to do so, a blog section has been created in each city's page. This section is

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divided into two parts, one featuring news from the city and the other with posts advertising events held in the area. These sections will be entirely managed by the KLC in the local language, following easy steps detailed in the instructions that can be found in the Reserved Area at this link.

Visual instructions can be found [here](#).

Social media

Social media profiles are central to engaging with local audiences and partners, building a network of people who can debate and act on relevant global issues and enforcing the dissemination.

Where?

To learn more about the project and find out how to get involved, all the targets can visit the IN-HABIT website: inhabit-h2020.eu

Or they may connect on social media:

FB: @inhabith2020

T: @INHABIT_H2020

LI: [linkedin.com/company/inhabit-h2020](https://www.linkedin.com/company/inhabit-h2020)

Opening an IN-HABIT local page - Guidelines

- Local communicators ought to keep in mind the visual and communication guidelines provided by Book on a Tree and they must communicate in the local language in order to reach the widest audience possible at a local level.
- Local pages ought to speak directly to the people who are addressed by the project. Therefore posts of engagement are particularly important for these pages, as they will create a sense of community and will provide feedback.

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- The most important news should be shared with the general page of IN-HABIT at the address inhabitsocial@bookonatree.com with an English translation and contextualization of what has been posted, so that they can be relaunched by the official IN-HABIT pages as well.
- Always remember to tag the official IN-HABIT page in every post and to use the planning tool provided to schedule the posts, in order to coordinate the communication between all the social media pages of IN-HABIT.

Who is the target audience?

At a local level: groups of citizens, associations, families, categories at risk of exclusion/disadvantage, sensitive collectives, local companies, universities and researchers, youth, schools and children, everyone involved in creating a relevant social impact.

How will an effective and engaging communication framework be implemented?

- Through real-time communication on global topics which are relevant for the IN-HABIT project.
- Through an advocational tone of voice where activism is communicated at the same time and a basic and clear communication on how to face everyday life and issues with a new mindset.
- Through the daily monitoring of the social media audience's conversations.
- By retweeting and reposting on relevant topics and issues, adding a caption to explain the project's specific interest, and replying to messages within a couple of hours if possible.
- By planning social posts but, at the same time, not forgetting to monitor trending hashtags.
- By identifying and selecting interesting opinion leaders to follow, with the hope of a follow back.
- By tagging project partners and using @EU_H2020 and #H2020 in every tweet to maximise their visibility expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

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What content should be shared?

Currently the content is scheduled and planned every two weeks, starting from a general plan in which a couple of month-long macro-campaigns are planned. Over the coming months, a strategy which can bring together the institutional communication strategy and the local one is expected to be co-defined with the help of the local communication managers. The editorial plan will therefore be split into five files (one for the institutional communication level and one file for each city). It will contain a complete calendar of international days and will help local communicators to find out how to share the project's messages at a local level and transfer IN-HABIT's messages and values into the local public debate.

In planning content, publication priority must be given, in order, to:

- ongoing events relevant to IN-HABIT, imminent and of high strategic and communicative value, particularly newsworthy and current;
- results achieved and relevant activities of the project partners and consortium members;
- press review on the project.

When?

Content will be posted two to four times a week on the project accounts (institutional communication) and an additional one or two localised posts for each city are expected. The mix of argumentation would vary depending on the phase of the project.

Use of common glossary and hashtags through the social profiles:

The use of common words is a key practice of IN-HABIT's DECO strategy because it contributes to achieving the goal of creating a shared code with all stakeholders and beneficiaries of the project since its inception. Therefore the Glossary will be used with the aim of making the meaning of each word unique and shared.

Hashtags will be used to increase outreach and join topic-specific conversations, to capitalise on existing trends, to group content and help people who are taking part in a specific event to

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find related posts and discussions on a specific topic, and to bring new opinions into said discussion.

→ Available document: [IN-HABIT GLOSSARY](#)

→ Available slide: [PROJECT'S OFFICIAL HASHTAGS](#)

9.1 Guidelines for effective communication at a local level

Available Tools

[General toolbox](#): Communication guidelines, visual identities, templates and video guides available

[Guidelines and references](#), including:

1. A video to better explain visual identity tips.
2. A shorter video including a shorter version for logo usage for external collaborators.
3. A guidelines FAQ video (following a survey among PPs).

[Project visual identity and graphic package](#), including templates and communication guidelines

All these tools have been approved and are ready for you to use.

Presentations Template

- *formal presentation* (for example, for external meetings, conferences and so on)
- *informal presentation* (for internal meetings, etc.)

In two versions:

lighter version, for download

complete version, for online use (like Teams, Drive or other collaborative spaces)

- *icon library* (separated - for easier, lighter use)

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Documents Template

- press release
- report
- meeting agenda
- meeting minutes
- deliverable
- letterhead
- simple document

In two versions:

Word (Office) version: downloadable, for offline work

Drive version: for documents needing collaborative approach and contribution from many partners, so we don't have to save several different versions thus reducing the chance of errors.

All of them have been tested to work properly on several devices.

IN-HABIT Visual Identity Guide

A simple tool with examples on how to use logos and imagery, dos and don'ts. This how-to guide should be of help in supporting you when visually expressing the project.

Logos

In the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

Patterns

Patterns to be used as background designs for your communication as well

Font Package

EU Flag graphics both in colour and b/w, including the project funding information

Iconography

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in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

Reference images (for presentations)

Free images for you to use in your presentations

Communication repository

Available [here](#) for press and communication releases.

Public materials also shared open access on the media section of the website.

Credentials for Reserved Area of website sent to all PPs

Instructions available [here](#)

Informative/communication material

Available [here](#)

- Project leaflets
 - 1 extended version in English published on the website, social media, and helpful as a reference for general audiences
 - 4 reduced versions in local languages, personalised for the 4 cities.
 - Both versions are in pdf format and already ready for online use and print. We used an A4 format and special attention to colour and readability so you can print it or fold it very easily in case you need to distribute it to meetings, even in black/white.
- Project general presentation for general audiences, in english
- 1 promotional video about the project, to be combined with 4 short local teaser videos (to be used in launch campaign for local customised dissemination)

In case of doubt, a more detailed manual on the Dissemination and Communication procedures can be accessed [here](#).

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10. Co-design of VIS

A key task of the IN-HUBs will be to enhance the process of co-designing Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS) aimed to improve IHW in the selected territories. The co-design process is the pillar around which the activity of the IN-HUB is centred. These activities take place according to the project agreement in the first half of the time plan, but it will follow up into the implementation of solutions during all the duration of the project. Co-design in IN-HABIT is therefore a general term that encompasses different activities that take place in different moments of the process, involve different stakeholders with different aims and beneficiaries, and require different tools and methods tailored according to specific local needs and contextual conditions.

Nonetheless, there are few key moments in which co-design has a central role within the activities of the IN-HUBs:

- in the assessment phase, co-designing with citizens key performance indicators to measure the impact of the project (see section 9).
- in the visioning and planning phase, as a way to co-produce the Inclusive Transformation Plans together with the people that will be mostly impacted by the outcomes of the project (see section 12).
- in the design of specific solutions that will be implemented on the territory as the consequence of the Inclusive Transformation Plans.

In this section we are dealing in particular with the last two tasks, which foresee a concrete involvement of inhabitants and territorial stakeholders in identifying key objectives and designing specific integrated solutions for improving health and well being in their territory. For this purpose, the local partners and LCAs who have a better understanding of local contexts and culture will select the appropriate tools and methods. In the following few key principles are proposed to inspire their choice among the many approaches and methods for inclusive and collaborative design according to the IN-HABIT philosophy.

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10.1 Contextual analysis (*reconnaissance*)

Engaging a wide and diverse group of stakeholders in producing a balanced and effectively shared understanding of a territory and its needs is a precondition to co-producing its transformation. Aside from the vast range of traditional methods like desk research, statistical survey, cost-benefit analysis, etc., IN-HABIT aims to devise and test a range of innovative methods for contextual analysis. Some of these have been already introduced elsewhere in this document: i.e stakeholder mapping process, (see chapter 7), or the gendered landscapes detailed in chapter 12.

One of the methods introduced during the LCAs training is Urban Reconnaissance, a flexible approach to reflect holistically about a given socio-spatial context. The [Urban Reconnaissance platform](#), developed by the ogino:knauss collective and Tesserae, provides a set of tools for the exploration of the complexity of factors that contribute to producing a given urban identity. The UR online device displays a collection of sixty-four different definitions of the word “city”, each one based on a different constitutive element or a disciplinary perspective of the urban. Altogether, the 64 definitions compose a matrix aimed at the interdisciplinary examination of the multiple interrelations and dependencies of urbanity. Each definition is accompanied by a related exercise for a spatial or thematic exploration inspired by that specific disciplinary or conceptual approach. The exercises in urban reconnaissance can be used to facilitate workshops, city walks and discussions, providing a comprehensive resource for engaging stakeholders and citizens in reflecting upon their socio-spatial context. The platform includes a [blog section](#) collecting examples of urban reconnaissance experiences done in the past, and a [downloadable manual](#) for designing different types of UR workshops.

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10.2 Pooling resources

Reconnaissance sessions and stakeholder mappings are important to identify, reach out and mobilise stakeholders, but the successive step is to pool skills and competences that can be employed as common resources to-coproduce and co-deploy solutions. An essential element for a successful co-design process is to transmit the sense that anybody can contribute and has some resource to bring into the process as well as some profit to gain. Among the suggested methods, the creation of a *Competence Abacus* is recommended. A competence abacus is a simple exercise in which local stakeholders or citizens present themselves both as carriers of specific skills and capacities and as potential beneficiaries for learning and acquiring competences.

Figure 20. Competence Abacus at INstabile Portazza, Bologna. Courtesy Luca Vandini, Kiez Agency.

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Simple templates can be prepared and filled to let participants let the others know what they can bring into the project as practical capacity or competence and what they would engage with, but also what they would be interested to learn. This process can facilitate the comprehension of what the team will be able to achieve, what are the weaknesses and what solutions are needed to increase the capacity of the group to accomplish its objectives. It is as well a tool to better exploit the knowledge exchange and capacity building potential of the project.

This step can also constitute the basis for actions for improving employability of citizens or connecting providers of skills and competences with business opportunity, like in the Inclusive Business Incubation program foreseen by IN-HABIT. Check also for this purpose the booklet [Economy and Skills](#) realised by City Mine(d) during the project EULER and the specific application developed in London with the [Elephant Path](#) project.

10.3 Visualising connections

The further key passage for an inclusive design is the attention to produce clear visualisations of the advancements of the process, and in particular in the creation of connections among different issues, capacities and responses. For this purpose is suggested the use of workshop methodologies as the [Thread Mapping](#) method adopted by Tesseract. This flexible methodology can be adapted to different purposes and different phases of a co-design process.

The point of the method is to use simple and intuitive material gestures to create collaborative maps and graphs, employing boards, pins, threads, and stickers that allow all participants to “put their hands on the map” independently from their skills. Different sections of a prepared board that can include maps, timelines, and thematic fields are connected using coloured threads pinned to the different points. Aside from the capacity to pin up effectively ideas and information shared in a intuitive visual form by heterogeneous groups, the method has the advantage to create a feeling of collective engagement, weaving together a fabric of informations and connections into a visually agreeable and semantically rich material artefact.

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This technique works also as an excellent icebreaker for activating people that may be intimidated by excessively verbal interactions.

The thread map can be used typically to transfer the above quoted abacus of competence into a localised action, connecting the personal profiles of the participants to specific locations or field of action, or to map key issues of a territory and crossing data and solutions. In the following a couple of examples on how they have been used in Tesseræ's projects:

Example 1: Kicking-off a co-design process at city level.

Used during the first public meeting of a co-design process at city level involving 12 different sites of experimentation, the board collected in the first section name, age, profession, competences and contacts of single citizens interested in taking part in the activities. Using the threads they were asked to connect their profiles with the project areas in which they were interested or had expertise to contribute, and finally to reach one of the four key project questions they wanted to discuss. The exercise led to the formation of four discussion tables opening the participative process.

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Figure 21. Thread Mapping in the kick-off of a co-design process.

Example 2: Co-designing a thematic map

The exercise was used during the development of a digital community atlas of the Südliche Friedrichstadt in Berlin. Each laboratory focused on a different layer map of the atlas, and this one was dedicated to transformations affecting the neighbourhood. The preliminary discussion was dedicated to agree on a taxonomy of the phenomena to be mapped. To do so, the first section of the board was used to collect different understanding of the word “transformation” in an urban context, and to group them in a range of essential categories of change that should be mapped in the atlas. After that first exercise, the participants were asked to provide examples of such types of transformation in the area. Therefore the threads were used to connect each one of these examples with analytical information about each case. This process was able in one round to design a critical taxonomy for the map and start the collection of data.

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Figure 22. Co-designing a thematic map with Thread Mapping.

10.4 Storytelling approach

The final recommendation for the effectiveness of the co-design process is to devote attention to narrate visions and collective processes from the perspective of the users. Co-design is not only a matter of deploying and implementing appropriate solutions, it is also about the engaged communities feeling ownership and acquiring agency. It is important to support stakeholders not only in identifying their solutions, but also in communicating their needs and claims, and to document the process that transforms the territory from a grassroots perspective.

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For this purpose Tesseractae proposes a set of tools and methods for collaborative storytelling which include prototype platforms for digital interactive storytelling, neighbourhood atlases and storytelling training modules that can be adapted flexibly to different scopes and target groups.

Platforms like [Narrability](#) or [CoMMA](#) are prototypes being developed for such purposes and are available for the IN-HUBS that want to test their use in the course of the co-design activities. They provide an alternative or a complement to traditional online media platforms and printed formats for collecting and publishing narratives produced by communities.

Furthermore, a training module for collaborative storytelling and the related template designed by Tesseractae to support workshops dedicated to collective storytelling processes is available for LCA. The template includes nine essential elements to tell a story effectively and is proposed as a basic tool to engage stakeholders in producing narrative accounts of the project advancements. It has been already adapted by the partner ISIM for the qualitative impact assessment through storytelling (see section 8.2).

The template and the instructions for setting storytelling workshops can be retrieved [here](#).

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11. Inclusive Transformation Plan (ITPlan)

The IN-HABIT Inclusive Transformation Plans are the Action Plans resulting from the co-design processes implemented with a GDEI perspective in the four IN-HUBs. These processes will be conducted with relevant stakeholders and local inhabitants and led by IN-HABIT city partners and trained facilitators to determine the spatial and functional elements of the IN-HUBs' activity, as well as the foreseen VIS to boost IHW in the selected urban areas.

The ITPlan, although sharing similar content with this document (D5.1), and the Inclusive Transition Pathways (D5.3), its main aim will be the one of identifying **priorities**, **objectives**, **activities** and **procedures** in order to establish a roadmap that leads to the implementation of the devised VIS. It will follow a similar structure in the four pilot cities to allow comparisons and evaluation.

In order to facilitate the elaboration of the document, in the following we provide the index that the project partners agreed on, including the contents that shape the ITPs.

Introduction

This section represents the point of departure, and as such it needs to include the initial plans for IHW solutions, as well as the main concepts related to the topic of each city.

IN-HUB establishment: organization, methods and achievements

This section reports all the steps that have been followed in order to establish the IN-HUBs, including therefore:

- A description of the consolidation of each city team, as well as the stakeholder mapping process.
- Communication campaign and open calls put in place to select the members of the local IN-HUBs.
- How the assignment of roles was implemented and a detail their specific tasks

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- Functioning of the IN-HUB: statute, principles, procedures, and incentives for participation

Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): top-down driven process

This section dives into the procedures and tools that have been used in collaboration with the project partners to initiate and steer the co-design process. As such, it includes:

- Working tools and guidelines used by LCAs, namely the ones presented in this document, as well as the training process of the LCAs.
- Process of co-design of IHW indicators.
- Process of secondary data collection
- Process of gender landscaping and its results.
- Process of carrying out surveys, interviews, and focus groups

Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): bottom-up participative process

This section addresses the procedures and tools that have been used in collaboration with the local communities to navigate the co-design process in the local context. As such, it includes:

- Co-design workshops facilitated by LCAs, with the involvement of local community representatives, their thematic approach and the results.
- Other methods/tools used for VIS co-design, their thematic approach and results.
- Organisation and development of the DFC workshops with educators, and future plans for inhabitants' engagement in mindset change activities.

City-specific VIS to boost IHW

This section gathers the results of the two previous sections, in order to clearly point out the outcomes and prospects for the implementation of the VIS in terms of:

- Initially planned IHW VIS.
- A description of the co-designed VIS.

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- A description of the co-deployment and co-management of each VIS: planned activities, resources, social procurement, PPPPs schemes, and expected outcomes...

Emerging lessons and recommendations

This section will include a final reflection on the challenges and achievements that were faced during the elaboration of the ITPs, more particularly:

- Challenges and achievements in the organization and development of the IN-HUB and PPPPs schemes.
- Challenges and achievements in combining bottom-up and top-down co-design, mindset change, and social innovations.
- Challenges and achievements in ensuring the GDEI perspective
- Assessment of and reflection on the GDEI Stakeholders Engagement Toolkit: methods and tools used in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of VIS
- Emerging recommendations at a city-specific level, but also at a comparative level among the cities.

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12. Inclusive Transition Pathway (ITPath)

Inclusive Transition Pathway (ITPath) stands for the multi-stakeholder participatory strategy developed within IN-HABIT, aimed at leading the co-design and implementation of local projects, with particular attention to the needs of people at risk of discrimination and exclusion. ITPaths consists of context-specific and inclusive co-management schemes defined with the involvement of local stakeholders. Each city will have its own ITP resulting from common principles of IN-HABIT and the co-design process with local stakeholders. They will include innovative financial schemes (e.g., community bartering, agreements of collaboration, social-public procurement schemes) to boost inclusive management and sustainable economic exploitation of regenerated spaces and the organisational model and specific functions of the IN-HUBs, which should function as a common pool resource agency to meet the demand and offer of voluntary work related to the sustainable co-management of re-designed public spaces. The creation of ITPaths will benefit from the common methodology for designing and managing public participation collaboratively pooled through the IN-HABIT WP5 and collected in this Toolkit.

The ITPath will trace the process of delivering VIS through the Public-Private-People Partnership in a synthetic and visual way, highlighting the key moments of the stakeholders' engagement process and collecting agreements, protocols and contractual documents produced to support the partnership in implementing the actions.

The ITPath will make use of the main tools presented in this toolkit to collect both the storyline (narrative) and the documentary stack (protocols and agreements) to report the advancement of the engagement process. In particular it will benefit from the regular use of Stakeholder Mapping Templates, Coordination Timelines, Engagement Diaries and other collaborative formats employed by the local community activators to track the activities on the field. Their combination will capture the evolution of the IN-HUBS and their capacity to co-design and deploy solutions, the formalisation and dynamism of the partnerships and their capacity to stabilise and multiply effects on the territory and to transfer innovations into larger contexts.

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In the following figure the foreseen structure of the ITPath.

Figure 23. Structure of the Inclusive Transition Pathways and its content

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Delivered at the end of the second year of the project timeline, ITPaths will resume the key agreements made for implementing the solutions. While the first 9 moments will be initiated and to a certain extent completed at the foreseen delivery of documents at M23, the last two steps will benefit from the delivered ITPaths as an essential preparatory step. The ITPath will provide a basis for the final evaluation of the implemented VIS and their impact on local IHW and will support the final report of the IN-HABIT activities with specific reference to the engagement of stakeholders with a GDEI approach.

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13. Gender landscapes

“Gender landscape refers to the gendered dimension of urban living. It recognises that people use the urban space differently because of various gendered structures, from the division of work, both paid and unpaid, to the role as carers, community leaders and networkers. It also considers how gender and sexuality are portrayed in communities, towns, cities and regions from a gender equality and diversity perspective. Viewing families, communities, towns, cities and regions from a gender equality and diversity perspective requires understanding of the main differences affecting the use of urban space.”

The gender and diversity landscapes aim to develop an integrated understanding of inclusion, gender equality and sustainable urban development. They will provide a set of tools, such as the geographical mapping of gender urban experiences, and good practices, gender mainstreaming for instance, to guide cities to become more inclusive through adequate sustainable urban development.

We envisage the IN-HABIT Gender landscape to be constituted by **three pillars: institutions, lived experiences, and health and well-being inequality**. The first pillar examines the integration of gender in decision-making. The second pillar adopts a group perspective to analyse the urban space on specific dimensions of life, such as work, education, caring, transport, leisure, etc. The last pillar analyses group differences in health and well-being from a spatial perspective. Each of the pillars has a specific objective within the overall aim of developing an integrated understanding of inclusion, gender equality, and sustainable urban development.

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Figure 24. Pillars of gender landscapes.

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Given the paucity of experiences on the establishment of gendered landscapes, this aspect of the project represents an opportunity for ground-breaking developments. We envisage that the gendered landscape will be fully integrated within the specific dimensions of intervention of each of the cities: culture, food, human-animal bonds and the environment. A participatory approach will ensure that the gendered landscape integrates the key aspects of each city and will serve policymakers and the public in the most effective way. This integrated approach will ensure that the various interlinkages, for instance between the economic, social and environmental aspects of the interventions, are properly taken into consideration. The approach to establishing gendered landscape will be in three phases: assessment, design, and implementation. The assessment stage includes stakeholder engagement and city-wide and area-specific assessment; the design stage will focus on the analysis of challenges and preparation of ideas and solutions; the implementation phase will include an action plan and sharing and validation.

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Figure 25. First pillar of gender landscapes.

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Pillar 1: Institutions

Each step of the design of an urban policy can produce discriminating effects. Commitment from policy makers represents arguably the first institutional element to consider. Publicly displaying their willingness to design an inclusive urban policy is essential but requires credible counterparts to demonstrate the policy makers' commitment. The existing legal framework can provide legally binding documents to set transparent and verifiable objectives supported by sex-disaggregated data. A fair representation and involvement in decision-making of all groups at relatively more risk of discrimination and exclusion help to take into account their needs and experiences. Mapping all the relevant stakeholders and resources involved, and their concrete actions contribute to the necessary transparency and accountability, for instance with a gender audit.

Finally, this pillar will produce an exhaustive mapping of the institutional framework that supported decision-making to gauge to which extent gender and diversity issues have been taken into account. This mapping will provide valuable information on how GDEI is institutionalised in decision making within the city, gaps and how these could be addressed.

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Lived experiences

To design an effective urban space,
we need to understand **how** people are using it.

1) Sampling

We survey respondents across the cities on the key dimensions of their daily life, such as work, education, caring, transport, leisure...

2) Estimation

We estimate the influence of the main determinants of individuals' behaviours and choices, including urban design and existing gender power structures.

3) Perspective taking

We simulate what would be the behaviours and choices of a group (e.g. women) under different circumstances (e.g. using bus instead of car).

4) Mapping

We represent the alternative scenarios in the current urban space to highlight its limitations.

5) Recommendations

These analyses will help to produce tailored recommendations.

Figure 26. Second pillar of gender landscapes.

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Pillar 2: Lived experiences

This pillar proposes to construct counterfactual scenarios to highlight how different groups experience the urban space. For instance, in Umeå, policymakers took the perspective of women in designing a tunnel that, consequently, had no sharp corners and additional light entrances, so that not just men felt secure when walking in the tunnel.

The outcomes of this pillar will be specific to the cities and align closely to the specific dimensions of intervention that IN-HABIT undertakes in each of the four cities. It will include geographical maps, co-designed with each city's population and Local Community Activators, describing the experience of the relevant groups under different circumstances. For instance, in the case of reaching a place of interest, the map would show the shortest path taken from the same starting point by women and men whether they are using a car or public transports, whether they need to drop kids at school before or not.

Each map will focus on one specific aspect at a time like public transportation, cultural representation, or accessibility to public services. These will be precious tools for policymakers, in the way they can be used to inform decisions on various aspects of the urban experience of different groups in the four cities.

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Health and well-being inequality

To understand how urban design affects health and well-being, we need to locate **where** health and well-being differ.

1) Sampling

We survey respondents across the cities and record their locations. It allows us to associate a measure of health and well-being at specific locations.

2) Kriging

We estimate health and well-being in non-sampled places which produces a heat map of health and well-being for the whole cities.

3) Contours

We locate precisely hot and cold spots of health and well-being using contour lines.

4) Inequality

We can reproduce the previous steps for another group (e.g. women). Then, we can identify locations where women have lower health and well-being.

5) Recommendations

These analyses will help to produce tailored recommendations.

Figure 27. Third pillar of gender landscapes.

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Pillar 3: Health and well-being inequality

The last pillar aims to identify the best and worst areas in each city in terms of health and well-being. It will yield geographical maps depicting hot and cold spots of health and well-being. This will allow us to measure whether gender and diversity groups are differently exposed to these specific spots and question the responsibility of urban design.

Building on the literature in geostatistics, we will survey respondents across the cities and record their geographical position. It allows us to associate a (continuous) measure of well-being at specific coordinates. The geostatistical technique known as *Kriging* can then be used to estimate well-being in non-sampled parts of the cities to produce a heat map of well-being for the whole city. Then, *hot and cold spots* can be characterized thanks to *contour lines* depicting pre-specified levels of well-being (e.g. +/- x standard deviations from the mean). Once hot and cold spots are identified, we can describe differences between individuals using *Oaxaca decompositions*, a statistical method widely used to analyze the sources of difference between individuals and groups.

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Institutions Dimensions	Lived experiences	Health and well-being inequality
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political • Administrative • Legal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work • Leisure / Sport • Transport • Caring • Education... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health • Well-being
<p>How</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political framework • Legal status • Structure and resources • Accountability mechanisms • GDEI strategies and implementation plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City surveys • Social experiments • Simulations of alternative scenarios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping hot and cold spots • Inequality analysis
<p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of gaps • Toolkits • Recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maps • Recommendations
<p>Data Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDEI political position • GDEI audits? • Initiatives based on a gender analysis? • Political appointment for GDEI? • Administrative officer for GDEI? • Budget for GDEI? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demography and socio- economic profiles for city and neighbourhoods • Residency data • City surveys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demography and socio- economic profiles for city and neighbourhoods • Residency data • City surveys

Figure 28. Gender landscapes' summary.

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14. Behavioural games

Common-pool resources and the lack of cooperation

As Ostrom (2006) describes them, “common-pool resources (CPR) are natural or man[sic]-made resources from which it is difficult to exclude or limit users once the resources are provided by nature or humans”. Consequently, once someone harvests some units, they are no longer available for others. Fishing grounds or forests are classic textbook examples of CPR. In the absence of any institution to regulate extraction of resources, individuals may harvest more than what the resources can sustain, leading to its exhaustion for everyone. This is what is known as “the tragedy of the commons”.

Behavioural games to foster cooperation in IN-HABIT

In IN-HABIT, each city implements a VIS related to their focus concept (food, culture, human-animal bond, art and environment). By co-designing it with the local inhabitants, the VIS constitutes a CPR in itself. Behavioural games are here to support the establishment of inclusive rules and institutions to overcome the tragedy of the commons and manage efficiently the newly created resource.

As very different groups are involved in the co-design, it is essential to understand their respective preferences and motivations to cooperate (or not) with everyone else. Very different factors, such as trust, social norms, stereotypes, or peer pressure, to name a few, may come into play. Each of these factors can be addressed with behavioural games.

Behavioural games to sustain change

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Because people tend to balance their virtuous behaviours over time, well-intentioned policies can lead to overall counterproductive effects by licensing people to behave badly (Mazar & Zhong, 2010). In the latter stages of IN-HABIT, behavioural games will be designed to help support and maintain change among the communities. They will contribute to solidify the new institutions and rules created to sustainably manage the CPR.

Based on insights gained from the previous IN-HABIT activities and the use of the IN-HABIT App on understanding a “day in the life” of local inhabitants, behavioural games will test solutions to promote the adoption of sustainable lifestyle. For instance, they may take the form of nudges, reminder and frequency of reminders, or information framing.

A simple example of behavioural games to test nudge effects is provided by Capraro et al. (2019). Participants are randomly separated into treatment and control groups before playing a cooperation game known as the Prisoner’s dilemma. In the treatment group, participants will be asked about the choice they believe to be morally right in this situation. Then, the game starts. Participants are all given 10€. They are then paired with another unknown participant and offered the possibility to keep it or give it to the other person. In the latter case, the receiver gets double that amount and the game ends. If the two participants cooperate they will get a higher reward than if both defect. However, if one betrays the other by not giving, he gets more than in any other situation. Finally, we get a measure of the nudge effect by comparing how many participants cooperate across treatment groups.

From a more practical perspective, Kroese et al. (2016) propose an interesting application to nudging healthy food choices. They selected three similar snack shops in a train station in the Netherlands, offering the same products, and nudged customers by manipulating the products displayed at the cash register. The first shop proposed only unhealthy snacks, the second shop only healthy snacks, and the last shop only healthy snacks and had an additional sign saying “we help you make healthier choices”. In the end, people seeing healthy snacks at the cash register were more prone to buy healthy products.

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15. I-Can method

A mindset is a mental attitude. It shapes our actions and our thoughts. Our mindset is our way of thinking, and our way of thinking can limit or empower oneself, in any number of ways.

Mindsets are considered to be a range of self-beliefs, with a fixed mindset on one end of a scale and a growth mindset on the other. Within this range, people with a fixed mindset believe their basic qualities, like their intelligence or talent, are simply fixed traits. A growth mindset implies a belief that people can change their abilities through effort. The main contrast between the two types of mindsets is around the idea of change. When people believe their abilities can change, they have greater perceived self-control over their outcomes and creates a love for learning and resilience that is essential for great accomplishments.

A mentality based on the I CAN come from the belief that everyone can be the protagonists of their lives, strike their own challenges, be sensitive with their environment and with the ones that are living together, and trust in their abilities to sort out challenges using the DFC methodology. This methodology gives the people the empowerment of conviction to do something to change their environment, set their challenges, change their lives through their ideas and their knowledge. Every story and idea is valued and listened to which gives them the conviction, the empowerment to change the world, their world, starting with the immediate challenges given the IN-HABIT project.

Therefore, as the DFC task is to switch communities to the I CAN Mindset, we follow a methodology that uses the principles of design thinking. This “formula” intentionally cultivates the I CAN Mindset through 5 steps: Feel, Do, Imagine, Evolute and Share.

Figure 29. Steps of the I CAN method.

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This methodology has been proven in over 70 countries around the world, built on the premise “Not by chance, by design”. This means that the participants are guided by a facilitator that has the training on not only the methodology but the main qualities that a facilitator must have: listening skills, proactive, resolute and great communicator.

This 5-step process based on Design Thinking provides its participants with the tools to develop abilities through the challenge-solving. The people trained in DFC apply them and adapt them according to their needs.

Once the necessary conditions are built, the co-design is the process to carry out a shared design between different people, each of whom contributes from their views and knowledge to achieve greater enrichment of the process.

How will the I-CAN method be applied in each city?

DFC proposes a set of workshops for educators in all cities. These workshops wish to introduce design and co-design activities within educational centers, and social and civil organizations. Its objective is to give the tools to educators to help the community (women, children, young people, people with disabilities...) become the primary actors and agents of change in their communities and environment given the framework of the IN-HABIT project in each city.

The DFC process will be taught as a 12- hour training or LAB. This DFC LAB goes through a systematized observation and the collective participation and reflection, through the different sequences of the mental process by diverging, converging, and synthesizing.

During the DFC process, and always in groups, each participant feels which is the topic that concerns them and, through a differences sequence, convergences and summary, they all choose a common action outbreak, that they later transform into a challenge; after that; each one imagines solution which is shared through a brainstorming; they choose one among everyone, they prototype it, share the result with other groups and learn the importance of the result with the other groups and learn the importance of giving and receive correct feedback; once finished, students do create an action plan, that is to say, not remaining at the “we must” or in the theoretical knowledge; after it, we think about what we have learned and evaluate (or said in another way: evaluation+evolution) and finally we share the result of the experience with everyone.

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What are the objectives of the workshops?

DFC Spain will develop a set of workshops in each city of the IN-HABIT project. This workshop is a 12-hour space called LAB I CAN where Design Thinking and social entrepreneurship converge. The target group for the workshops is educators that will take these tools to develop the process with their beneficiaries with DFC follow-up and guidance. The DFC LAB objectives are:

- To understand the mindset change and how to get there: experimentation
- To provide new tools to educators through the DFC methodology for them to use with their beneficiaries: implementation
- To become a practitioner of the DFC methodology. DFC will choose the most motivated participants (2 from each city) to have a final training to become facilitators

How is the LAB I CAN structured?

The basic structure is:

1. The history, the origin of the initiative
2. The work process (experimenting the whole process)
3. The facilitation of projects with the methodology (participants practice to then reflect on the key aspects of facilitation)
4. Looking at the future. How to put this into practice (a space to facilitate the transition to action)

In the course sessions, there will be 2 permanent facilitators so that they can meet the needs of the participants. The LAB I CAN is structured in three blocks.

Block 1: Introduction

- Generating interaction with the participants
- Explaining the origins and foundations of the methodology, as well as showing some examples

Figure 30. LAB I CAN: interaction with the participants.

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Block 2: Experiencing the process

- Introducing the framework, so that you can connect emotionally with it.
- Experiencing each of the phases:

FEEL: the whole group working on the framework until it is possible to identify a focus of action
IMAGINE: working in groups to develop solutions to the selected focus and prototyping the solution
DO: in pairs, teams test prototypes developed by the other team and give feedback
EVOLUATE: in groups reflect on the experience
SHARE: each group shares both what was lived and what was reflected differently, taking care of the storytelling

Figure 31. Participants working on the phases in the LAB I CAN.

After having experienced the process, each of the steps is reviewed in detail, and projects carried out with the methodology are reviewed

Figure 32. Facilitating the I CAN method.

Block 3: The keys to facilitation

- Facilitating in the first person, divided into 2 groups, some participants carry out the facilitation of the FEEL phase, after each intervention, there is feedback from the assistants and the facilitators

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- By compiling the keys to facilitation, after first-person experimentation and with what was observed during what was experienced during the process, the keys that must be taken into account when facilitating the process are identified.
- Looking to the future: a space to facilitate the step to action and the review of the key aspects to take into account to identify the ideas that will later be developed through the Bridge for Billions platform
- Workshop closing dynamics

DFC will hand over to the educators the [DFC toolkit](#), as well as the templates that will help them gather the information on the solutions that the beneficiaries come up with.

After the workshop, participants will have follow-up sessions to:

- Help them develop the framework in which they will work, given the needs and topics targeted in each city.
- Answer any questions they may have (before, during, and after the DFC process).

When will the workshops take place?

Meetings with local partners and community activators will be held to: identify the educators and to give the key information on the LAB.

The DFC LABs will be done each year covering the KPIs for each city but not limited to this. Each city will have 33% of the educators for the first year, 33% in the second year and 33% the third year. **We count year one from month 13 of the project (September 2021)**

Who are the target groups of the workshops?

As cities are working on specific areas and topics, LCAs do not have to limit the identification of educators to the area or neighborhood. If they see potential educators that are motivated and want to be part of IN-HABIT, they are welcome, even though they are part of the broader community.

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This identification will serve as a baseline to establish a schedule for the workshops that LCAs will join and help and become the communication channel with educators. Each of the workshops will be introduced to the local calendar set up for IN-HABIT activities.

We define educators as people that work regularly with the different beneficiaries that we wish to reach for the IN-HABIT project. For example, educators are: teachers (children and young people), facilitators and trainers in associations and NGOs, professionals working on a regular basis with the different groups: women, elderly, people with disabilities and all relevant groups within each city. It is important that the educator works with the group ideally in an organization, if not at least to have been working with the community for 3 years.

As identification of the educators is key to design and schedule the DFC LABS, information on the educators will be gathered by the LCAs. The main information needed is:

- Name
- Gender
- Name of the organization, NGO, association
- Beneficiaries (children, young people, families, people with disabilities ..)
- Number of beneficiaries do they often work on
- How often does the educator work with the beneficiaries
- If the educator has experience with trainings and workshops
- If the educator could have the training in english

After this information is gathered and analyzed, meetings with local partners will be held to select educators and schedule the first round of Mindset Change workshops. Every year will have the same procedure: identification, analysis and schedule of the DFC LABs.

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16. IN-HABIT App

The IN-HABIT App will provide access to innovative behavioural games and activities as developed by WP6 and WP7; it will be geolocalized in the cities involved in the project, with a flexible and upgradeable architecture. A first version will be delivered in month 28 (December 2022), and then tested in each city until final delivery in month 36 (August 2023).

The app will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: it is like a friendly fellow citizen. The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and at this point communicate the following with them (through PUSH notifications):

- a) content by spatial proximity (you're close to something that interests you and maybe you're not aware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- b) content by temporal proximity (an event next week, a discount for something useful);
- c) communications about activities, discounts, offers you're entitled to.

On the other hand, it allows the user to communicate requests, report disservices etc. directly to the city administrations (PULL), and respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results, and data (movement, activities, reading, consultations) on inhabitants' use of the city, are delivered – in an anonymous form – to the administrators.

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17. IN-HABIT Platform

The aim of the IN-HABIT platform is to bring together decision makers, operators and inhabitants by creating a sustainable and interoperable data platform (accessible by web) which will be connected to other city or regional data management systems.

IN-HABIT platform will retrieve, integrate, manage and visualize data from various data sources (sensors, cameras, open data repositories, observational programmes such as Copernicus and GEOSS, and the IN-HABIT App) which will be processed to show valuable information into specific dashboards to help managers in decision-making processes.

Main Features

- The IN-HABIT platform delivers datasets and connects users, systems and data in the areas of interventions, with dashboards, fleet overview of all equipment (IoT, sensors) on a geographical site, with monitoring and notifications and with APIs (programmable interfaces) to interconnect with other systems and with specific user interfaces.
- The IN-HABIT platform is based on FIWARE because it guarantees an open, robust, and compliant with the data protection regulation platform, ensuring cybersecurity and contributing with the interoperability among different communication standards.
- It is also suited for the collection of various time series data sources and IoT, the online running of algorithms processing these data, the alerting through SMS or email and the visualization through dashboards. It can support multiple customers and multiple industrial IoT applications in a multi-tenant way.
- The platform will also integrate data from the IN-HABIT APP, which uses geolocation for collaborative urban planning, citizen engagement and monitoring. Open data on cultural and food consumptions (from libraries, theatres, food markets etc.) will be gathered and analysed, with the IN-HABIT platform complementing these analyses.

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Benefits

- Creation of an intelligent system for inclusive health and well-being in cities management based on the huge amount of data and the use of continuous 'big data' analytics (high dimensional multi view data).
- Connectivity between different subsystems and the smart management of infrastructures allowed by deep neural networks based on prediction and optimisation techniques.
- Builds upon open data technologies of Smart City projects (e.g. Synchronicity EU Project, Smart Costa del Sol) and capitalizes the experience gained to provide dynamic management of cities.
- Creates secure, open and consistent data about the performance and impacts of the deployed solutions in the four IN-HABIT cities.
- Integrates Key Impact Indicators (KIIs) to measure changes on people's health and well-being co-designed and tested.
- Shows the evolution of IHW in the 4 pilot areas before and (two years) after the implementation of the Visionary integrated solution (VIS).

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18. Data Management

IN-HUBs activities will require the collection and elaboration of text and multimedia data generated in the meetings, interviews, surveys, focus groups, IN-HABIT App, and online activities. In this respect, and according with the [D9.2 “Data Management Plan” \(DMP\)](#) submitted to the EC in February 2021 and downloadable with your IN-HABIT credentials from the link above, specific data requirements should be followed by community activators and other participants in the IN-HUBs, related to:

- Types and formats of generated/collected data
- The re-use of any existing data, and how
- Details of data origins
- Expected size of the data
- Data Utility

All the collected/generated data in the IN-HUBs should be fair, which refers to the specific data management rules that are made explicit in the DMP: **findable, openly accessible, interoperable, and re-usable.**

In terms of data security, the DMP includes also rules related to:

- Provisions in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)
- Data storage
- Data breaches
- Data destruction
- Data protocols for surveys, interviews and workshops
- Transfer of data

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The main ethical issues for IN-HABIT concern “*Research involving Human beings and the Protection of Personal Data*”. All the internal procedures needed to assure the compliance with the requirements have been so far developed in [D9.3 “Ethics Requirements”](#) submitted to the EC in February 2021, which you can download with your IN-HABIT credentials from the link above. The responsibility for ensuring that the conduct of the research is in line with the ethical principles, rests with the lead investigator in each WP. WP9 is responsible for the development of the processes and procedures for ethical clearance (including the development of an informed consent form) and for the implementation and central project management of ethical clearance documentation.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Pilot cities' task and deliverables

Pilot Cities' Deliverables

The four pilot cities, represented by WPs 1-4, will conduct a series of tasks over the duration of IN-HABIT with the support of project partners from all WPs. These tasks will be carried out, as far as possible, in parallel in the four cities to facilitate mutual learning and knowledge exchange.

In the following table it is represented a list of tasks of WP1-4, the lead project partners, and the other partners involved:

Tasks WP1-4	Leading Partner	Project Partners involved
X.1 Establishment of the IN-HUB	UCO/BSC/LUCCA/SUA	AVUE, CORDOBA (WP1) / RPR, KQ (WP2) / UNIPI, LCREA (WP3) / NITRA, HIDE (WP4) / TSR, BOT, WTG, LABORELEC (WP1-4)
X.2 Co-design of VIS	TSR-UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	CORDOBA, AVUE (WP1) / BSC, KQ (WP2) / RPR, LUCCA (WP3) / SUA, NITRA, HIDE (WP4) / UREAD, DFC, ISIM, BOT, LABORELEC, WTG (WP1-4)
X.3 Co-deployment of VIS	CORDOBA/KQ/LUCCA/SUA	UCO, AVUE (WP1) / RPR, BSC (WP2) / UNIPI, LCREA (WP3) / NITRA, HIDE (WP4) / LABORELEC, WTG, TSR, UREAD, BOT, DFC (WP1-4)

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X.4 Co-management of VIS	UCO/BSC/LUCCA/SUA -HIDE	CORDOBA, AVUE (WP1) / KQ, RPR (WP2) / UNIPI, LCREA (WP3) / NITRA (WP4) / UREAD, TSR, B4B, DFC (WP1-4)
X.5 Monitoring and evaluation of VIS	UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	CORDOBA, AVUE (WP1) / KQ, RPR (WP2) / LUCCA, LCREA (WP3) / NITRA, HIDE (WP4) / UREAD, TSR, ISIM, LABORELEC, WTG (WP1-4)
X.6 Upscaling and Replication Activities	UCO/RPR/LUCCA/NITRA	All Partners

Table 13. List of Tasks for WP1-4 and partners involved.

Pilot Cities' Deliverables

In parallel to the completion of tasks X.1-6 of WP1-4, a series of public deliverables will be produced. A list of these and the leading partner in charge of its completion can be found in Table 3:

Deliverables WP1-4	Leading Partners	Delivery date
D X.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan	UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	28th February 2022
D X.2 Innovative PPPPs and financial mechanisms for IHW	UCO/BSC,UNIPI/SUA	31st August 2025
D X.3 Monitoring and evaluation VIS for IHW Midterm report	UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	31st August 2024
D X.4 Monitoring and evaluation of VIS for IHW Final report	UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	31st August 2025
D X.5 Upscaling Plan	UCO/BSC/UNIPI/SUA	31st August 2025

Table 14. List of Deliverables for WP1-4, leading partner and delivery date.

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